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Effects of Rejuvenator - a Local Commercial Libido and Fertility Drink on LD₅₀, Body Weight Changes, Antioxidants and Oxidative Stress Parameters on Male Wistar Albino Rats

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ABSTRACT

Rejuvenator is a locally produced commercial drink widely marketed as a libido and fertility enhancer. Despite its popularity, there is limited scientific evidence regarding its safety and physiological effects. This study investigated the median lethal dose (LD₅₀), body weight alterations, and antioxidant and oxidative stress parameters associated with Rejuvenator administration in male Wistar albino rats. Twenty-five male rats were randomly assigned into five groups (n = 5 per group). Group 1 served as the control and received placebo; Group 2 received Viagra (100 mg/kg); Groups 3, 4, and 5 received low (100 mg/kg), medium (200 mg/kg), and high (400 mg/kg) doses of Rejuvenator, respectively. All animals had free access to food and water. The administration lasted three weeks, during which body weight was monitored weekly. At the end of the study, animals were fasted, anesthetized with chloroform, and sacrificed. Blood samples were collected by cardiac puncture for biochemical analyses of antioxidant enzymes - superoxide dismutase (SOD), catalase (CAT), and malondialdehyde (MDA). Data were analyzed using one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA), and differences were considered significant at $p < 0.05$. No mortality was recorded during the experiment, indicating a LD₅₀ greater than 5000 mg/kg body weight. Medium-dose Rejuvenator administration produced a significantly higher percentage increase in body weight ($14.46 \pm 0.45\%$) compared to the control ($7.86 \pm 0.82\%$), Viagra ($8.43 \pm 0.96\%$), and low-dose ($9.76 \pm 0.64\%$) groups. Superoxide

dismutase concentration was significantly lower in the Viagra group (36.32 ± 3.90) compared to the control (51.89 ± 1.15), while medium (48.43 ± 1.60) and high (49.52 ± 4.00) doses of Rejuvenator improved Superoxide dismutase activity. Catalase levels were significantly reduced in the Viagra (44.20 ± 2.90) and low-dose Rejuvenator (48.68 ± 2.00) groups compared to the control (65.51 ± 1.91). No significant differences were observed in Malondialdehyde levels across groups. Rejuvenator exhibited no acute toxicity and did not promote oxidative stress in male Wistar rats. The drink may enhance antioxidant enzyme activity and promote body weight gain, suggesting potential physiological effects that warrant further investigation.

Keywords: Rejuvenator, libido and fertility drink, antioxidants, oxidative stress, Superoxide dismutase (SOD), Catalase (CAT), Malondialdehyde (MDA)

1. INTRODUCTION

Rejuvenator energy drink is a herbal energy drink and aphrodisiac consumed extensively in most parts of Nigeria. Although it is branded and sold in most shops, it has not been registered by the National Agency for Food, Drug Administration and Control (NAFDAC), an agency of government charged with the regulation of production and consumption of drugs and food materials.

Despite this, people consume this herbal concoction mainly due to its alleged efficacy. The container label shows that it contains the following: *Tribulus terrestris*, *Capsasine*, *Cilantroside*, *Myristica fragrans*, *Zingiber officinale*, *Rhodiola rosea*, *Ocinum bacilicum*, honey and cinnamon. According to the manufacturers, a single dose of half tumbler daily taken consecutively for one week will correct any form of erectile dysfunction in men and increase libido and fertility in both men and women, a claim that is scientifically unverified. Owing to the high consumption rate, the present study investigated the chemical profile of this herbal concoction by quantifying the phytochemicals, heavy metals, vitamins, minerals, and proximate composition. (Adindu et al, 2023).

Sexual drive is influenced by biological, psychological, and social factors, but it can also be affected by medications and medical conditions. Many prescription drugs and narcotics (e.g., antidepressants, anxiolytics, antihistamines, antihypertensive, adrenergic receptor blockers, antipsychotics, and opioids) can negatively impact sexual desire, inhibit erection, ejaculation, or orgasm, and so on. Contrariwise, many aphrodisiac substances can improve sexual performance. In particular, substances of natural origin have been used worldwide for millennia in traditional medicines to boost sexual desire, sexual pleasure, or sexual behavior (Neelesh, 2022).

Red Ginseng (*Panax ginseng*): *P. ginseng* is used to treat anxiety, athletic/physical stamina, cognitive function, depression, male fertility, migraines, immunostimulants, menopausal hot flashes, and impotence. Both American and Asian ginseng can boost energy, lower blood sugar and cholesterol, reduce stress, induce relaxation, treat diabetes, and control sexual dysfunction in men. The libido-boosting properties of *P. ginseng* may stem from its stress-relieving properties. Ginseng may help with infertility by improving sexual performance, sperm count, and quality

Pumpkin (*Cucurbita moschata*) seeds: According to Chinese medicine, pumpkin seeds are excellent and have antidepressant properties. Eating pumpkin seeds can affect the health of

a man's prostate, which is essential for male sexual health. It improves the functioning of the prostate gland as well as the hormones in males. Myosin is essential for the contraction of muscles, and pumpkin seeds are a good source of it (Purnamasari *et al.*, 2022).

Walnuts (*Juglans* spp.): The results of the study led the study's authors to the conclusion that incorporating walnuts, hazelnuts, and almonds into an unhealthy western diet may increase sexual desire (libido), as well as an improvement in the quality or intensity of orgasms. Walnuts are an excellent source of omega-3 fatty acids, which are heart-healthy fats that increase dopamine levels. Walnuts are also a good source of arginine, which is an amino acid that stimulates the body's production of nitric oxide, which in turn relaxes blood vessels and boosts circulation (Olabiya *et al.*, 2022).

Avocado (*Asparagus officinalis*): Avocado's high levels of folic acid aid in the metabolization of proteins, which gives men more energy. Avocado is a versatile culinary delight. They contain vitamin E, which is beneficial to the nails and skin. Avocados are high in vitamin B6, potassium, and monounsaturated fats. These promote healthy circulation and a strong heart, both of which are required for sex. Avocados naturally protect the arteries. Erectile dysfunction is more common in men with heart disease. Avocado consumption lowers the risk of metabolic syndrome, which is a risk factor for erectile dysfunction (Yee *et al.*, 2022).

Honey: Honey plays a crucial role in maintaining sexual health. Because it's full of natural sugars, it gives people more stamina and makes it possible to stay in bed for longer. Honey also has boron, a mineral that has been shown to have the ability to control both hormone levels and nitric oxide production. This vasodilator is released into the bloodstream during sexual excitement, and its role is to widen blood vessels. In other words, it causes the blood vessels to become more expansive (IsHak *et al.*, 2017).

Maca Root (*Lepidium meyenii*): Maca (*Lepidium meyenii*) is an Andean plant of the brassica (mustard) family. Preparations from Maca root have been reported to improve sexual function. Maca root has been associated with potential aphrodisiac and fertility-enhancing properties in both animal models and human studies. Research suggests it may influence reproductive hormone levels and improve sperm quality. Preparations from the maca root have been reported to improve sexual function in healthy populations.

Antioxidants and oxidative stress: Nutritional utilization of antioxidants, such as vitamins C, E, β -Carotene and micronutrients, such as folate and zinc, have been shown to be critically essential for normal semen quality and reproductive function. However, it is still, a large knowledge gap exists concerning the role of antioxidants on semen parameters and the role in treatment of male subfertility. (Houda *et al.*, 2021)

Antioxidants: Antioxidants are the organism's means of defense against the destructive effects of ROS production and accumulation (Monroy *et al.*, 2013). The exposure of living cells to the harmful effects of free radicals triggers reactions that activate multiple internal defense mechanisms, which helps the body in the removal of free radicals and their derivatives (Mirończuk-Chodakowska *et al.*, 2018). Antioxidants engage in three major functions: preventing, repairing, and deactivating the detrimental effects of ROS (Shahidi *et al.*, 2010).

Generally, antioxidants in living cells can be classified into two primary groups based on their mode of action on the ROS, enzymatic and non-enzymatic antioxidants (Kosten *et al.*, 2013).

Oxidative stress and its effect on intercourse (Erectile Dysfunction): Reasonably sufficient erectile and sexual functionality is essential for men. Sexual activities improve the quality of life in men and promote longevity. It has been reported that erectile dysfunction (ED)

is a major challenge in men, which is estimated to be encountered by 40% of ≥ 40 -year-old males (Gratzke *et al.*, 2010).

Erectile Dysfunction (ED) can develop due to psychological, endocrine, vascular, neurological, and immune factors acquired via environmental exposure, lifestyle and underlying pathology (Paolicchi *et al.*, 1996). The regular final mechanism of ED is vascular failure of the penis driven by significant corporal smooth muscle dysfunction which is mediated and skyrocketed via intracellular oxidative stress culminating in a rise in smooth and endothelial muscle cell dysfunction with increase in the rate of apoptosis (Gratzke *et al.*, 2010). Nitric oxide (NO) is essential for adequate erection via Nitric Oxide Synthase transcription (NOS) to bring about vasodilation as well as penile engorgement with blood. On this basis the regular vascular failure mediator in ED is inflammation and OS, this it does through NOS reduction and subsequent reduction in NO. Dysfunctional endothelial cells and increase in cellular adhesion molecules caused by inflammation enhance local arteriosclerosis and hardening of the vasculature which in turn result in local inflammation and OS (Paolicchi *et al.*, 1996).

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The materials used in this project includes an electronic weighing balance, hand gloves, face mask, sterile syringes, dissecting sets, cotton wool, saw dust, water, Viagra, sample bottle, cages, bowl plates, grower feed, chloroform, tissue, enamel stainless plate, formalin, centrifuge, spectrophotometer, ELISA kit.

2. 1. Preparation of Extract

A bottle of Rejuvenator energy drink was bought from a retail store in Aba, Abia State, Nigeria. The sample was sent to Docchy Analytical Laboratories and Environment Services Limited in Nnewi, Anambra State, Nigeria for analyses.

2. 2. Determination of LD50

Lethal Dose (LD₅₀) was estimated according to the method of Chinedu *et al.* (2013). This method involved three phases (Phase 1-3), as summarized in Table 3, and the mortality outcome is illustrated in Figure 1.

2. 2. 1. Phase 1

This phase had nine animals. The nine animals were divided into three groups with three animals each. Each group was administered different doses (100, 200 and 500 mg/kg respectively) of test substance. The animals were placed under observation for 24 hours to monitor their behaviour as well as occurrence of mortality.

2. 2. 2. Phase 2

This phase also involved the use of nine animals distributed into three groups of three animals in each group. Doses of test substance was stepped up to 1000, 1500 and 2000 mg/kg respectively. The animals were observed for 24 hours to monitor their behaviour as well as mortality.

2. 2. 3. Phase 3

The phase required the use of nine experimental animals divided into three groups of three animals each. The animals were administered higher doses (3000, 4000 and 5000 mg/kg) of test substance and then observed for 24 hours to monitor behaviour as well as mortality. This was the final stage of testing and here no mortality was recorded at this stage, the LD50 of test substance is said to be greater than 5000 mg/kg and hence has a high degree of safety.

Table 1. Experimental Design and animal groups treated with Standard drug (Viagra) and Rejuvenator extract.

S/N	Groups	Administered Dosage	Number of animals
1	Normal Control	Placebo	5
2	Viagra	Viagra (100 mg/kg body weight)	5
3	Low Dose	Extract (100 mg/kg body weight)	5
4	Medium Dose	Extract (200 mg/kg body weight)	5
5	High Dose	Extract (400 mg/kg body weight)	5

2. 3. Handling of Animals

Twenty-five (25) albino Wistar rats weighing 50-80g were obtained from the Animal Facility of the College of Medical Sciences, University of Calabar. All rats were housed in step-B plastic cages (temperature 25 °C, relative humidity 50-60- and 12/12-hour light-dark cycle) and allowed to acclimate to a standard diet and water *ad libitum* for 28 days before being used for the experiment after growing to a substantial weight range between 150-200g. The rats were divided into 5 groups of 5 animals each and the treatments were as shown in table 1 above.

2. 4. Administration of Extract

The various doses of extract and the standard drug (Viagra) were administered orally to each assigned group via the use of an oral gavage. Duration of administration was 21 days.

2. 5. Sample Collection

After the 21-day experimental period, the animals were fasted overnight by removing food with constant access to water. Before sacrifice, the test animal was anaesthetized with chloroform via inhalation. Whole blood was gotten through the heart with sterilized syringes and needles. The blood sample was emptied into plain test tube bottles and left standing for 2 hours at 4 °C. The blood sample was centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 10 minutes to obtain serum from the cells. The serum was separated into simple test tubes using sterilized syringes and needles and stored frozen until required for biochemical analysis. Testes and liver tissues were

removed and blotted with Whatman No 1 filter paper to clean the excess blood on the organs. The remaining tissue was used for biochemical analysis.

2. 6. Biochemical Analysis

Oxidative Stress Assay

Determination of Superoxide Dismutase (SOD) activity

Superoxide Dismutase activity was determined by its ability to inhibit the auto-oxidation of epinephrine determined by the increase in absorbance at 480 nm as described by Sun and Zigma (1978). The reaction mixture (3 ml) contained 2.95 ml 0.05 M sodium carbonate buffer pH 10.2, 0.02 ml of the sample and 0.03 ml of epinephrine. HCL was used to initiate the reaction. The reference cuvette contained 2.95 ml buffer, 0.03 ml of substrate (epinephrine) and 0.02 ml of water. Enzyme activity was calculated by measuring the change in absorbance at 480 nm for 5 minutes.

Determination of Catalase activity

Catalase activity was determined according to Sinha, *et al.* (1972) by measuring the decrease in absorbance at 620 nm due to the decomposition of H₂O₂ in a UV recording spectrophotometer at intervals of 60 seconds for 5 mins. It was assayed colorimetrically at 620 nm and expressed as μ moles of H₂O₂ consumed/min/mg protein at 25 °C. The reaction mixture (1.5 ml) contained 1.0 ml of 0.01M phosphate buffer (pH 7.0), 0.1 ml of the sample and 0.4 ml of 2M H₂O₂. The reaction was stopped by the addition of 2.0 ml of dichromate-acetic acid reagent (5% potassium dichromate and glacial acetic acid were mixed in 1:3 ratio).

Lipid Peroxidation

Malondialdehyde (MDA) an index of lipid peroxidation was determined using the method of Buege and Aust (1978). 1.0 ml of the sample was added to 2 ml of (1:1:1 ratio) TCA-TBA-HCl reagent (thiobarbituric acid 0.37%, 0.24N HCl and 15% TCA) tricarboxylic acid-thiobarbituric acid-hydrochloric acid reagent boiled at 100 °C for 15 min, and allowed to cool. Flocculent materials were removed by centrifuging at 3000 rpm for 10 min. The supernatant was removed and the absorbance read at 532 nm against a blank. MDA was calculated using the molar extinction coefficient for MDA-TBA - complex of $1.56 \times 10^5 \text{ M}^{-1}\text{CM}^{-1}$.

Assay of Glutathione Peroxidase (GPx)

To 0.2 ml Tris buffer, 0.2 ml EDTA, 0.1 ml Sodium azide and 0.2 ml of sample were added and mixed well. To this 0.2 ml of GSH followed by 0.1 ml of H₂O₂ were added. The contents were mixed and incubated at 37 °C for 10 minutes. The reaction was stopped by the addition of 0.5 ml 10% TCA. The activities were expressed as μ g of GPx consumed/min/mg protein (Rotruckjt *et al.*, 1973).

2. 7. Statistical analysis

The statistical package for the social science (SPSS Version 21.2) was used to analyse the result. The raw data obtained was analysed using one-way ANOVA and followed by post-hoc (Least square difference) comparison of the groups. Differences at $P < 0.05$ were considered statistically significant. Values were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation.

3. RESULTS

3. 1. Body-weight comparison in Experimental Groups

The effect of the administration of Viagra and different doses of Rejuvenator on body weight and percentage body-weight change is presented in Table 2. No significant changes ($p > 0.05$) were noted in body weight of experimental animals. Treatment with Medium Dose (14.46 ± 0.45) showed significantly higher ($p < 0.05$) % body-weight change compared against Control (7.86 ± 0.82), Viagra (8.43 ± 0.96) and Low Dose (9.76 ± 0.64) groups.

Table 2. Percentage body weight change in experimental groups.

Groups	Bodyweight (g)				%Bodyweight Change
	Day 0	Day 7	Day 14	Day 21	
Control	166.7 ± 3.40	182.6 ± 4.28	198.2 ± 2.77	177.6 ± 2.89	7.86 ± 0.82
Viagra	162.2 ± 7.65	178.7 ± 7.60	189.6 ± 3.79	172.9 ± 2.49	8.43 ± 0.96
Low Dose	163.7 ± 5.50	176.3 ± 8.17	195.3 ± 14.80	186.8 ± 2.97	9.76 ± 0.64
Medium Dose	155.8 ± 5.66	167.9 ± 5.75	183.9 ± 11.19	174.3 ± 12.97	$14.46 \pm 0.45^{*,a,b}$
High Dose	160.7 ± 3.40	180.0 ± 5.37	205.5 ± 9.34	178.1 ± 9.19	9.03 ± 0.35^c

Values are presented as Mean \pm SEM, n = 3

* = significantly different from Control at $p < 0.05$

a = significantly different from Viagra at $p < 0.05$

b = significantly different from Low Dose at $p < 0.05$

c = significantly different from Medium Dose at $p < 0.05$

3. 2. LD50 result

Table 3. Lethal Dose determination of rejuvenator extract.

Dosage	Mortality
Phase 1	
100	0
200	0
500	0
Phase 2	
1000	0

1500	0
2000	0
Phase 3	
3000	0
4000	0
5000	0

LD50 results showed no mortality rate therefore the extract in dosage of below 5000 mg/kg is safe for consumption. The dosage-mortality data are shown in Table 3, and the result is graphically illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Mortality outcome of Rejuvenator LD₅₀ test.

3. 3. Antioxidant concentration of Experimental Groups

Table 4. Antioxidant concentrations in experimental groups.

Groups	SOD (µmol/ml)	CAT (µmol/ml)	MDA (µmol/ml)	GPx (µmol/ml)
Control	51.89 ± 1.15	65.51 ± 1.91	8.10 ± 0.87	4.91 ± 0.30
Viagra	36.32 ± 3.90*	44.20 ± 2.90*	7.16 ± 0.80	4.20 ± 0.40

Low Dose	42.91 ± 1.90	48.68 ± 2.00*	7.43 ± 0.80	4.56 ± 0.40
Medium Dose	48.43 ± 1.60 ^a	54.29 ± 4.60	7.26 ± 0.40	4.37 ± 0.10
High Dose	49.52 ± 4.00 ^a	56.03 ± 3.70	8.03 ± 0.60	4.67 ± 0.30

Values are presented as Mean ± SEM, n = 3

* = significantly different from Control at p < 0.05

a = significantly different from Viagra at p < 0.05

3. 3. 1. Superoxide Dismutase concentrations in Experimental Groups

The effect of the administration of Viagra and doses of Local Rejuvenator on superoxide dismutase (SOD) concentration is presented in Figure 2a below. There was a significant reduction (p<0.05) of SOD concentration in Viagra group (36.32 ± 3.90) compared to the Control group (51.89 ± 1.15). Administration of MD (48.43 ± 1.60) and High dose (49.52 ± 4.00) showed significant improvement in SOD concentration compared to the Viagra group.

The summary of all antioxidant parameters, including SOD, catalase (CAT), malondialdehyde (MDA), and glutathione peroxidase (GPx), is presented in Table 4, while their graphical representations are shown in Figure 2a–d.

Figure 2(a-d). (a) SOD concentrations, (b) Catalase concentrations in experimental groups, (c) Malondialdehyde concentrations in experimental groups, (d) Glutathione peroxidase concentrations in experimental groups.

3. 3. 2. Catalase concentrations in Experimental Groups

The effect of the administration of Viagra and doses of Local Rejuvenator on catalase (CAT) concentration is presented in Figure 2b below. Viagra and Rejuvenator (Low Dose) groups showed significant reductions ($p < 0.05$) in catalase concentrations (44.20 ± 2.90 and 48.68 ± 2.00 , respectively) compared to the Control group (65.51 ± 1.91).

3. 3. 3. Malondialdehyde concentrations in Experimental Groups

The effect of the administration of Viagra and doses of Local Rejuvenator on Malondialdehyde (MDA) concentration is presented in Figure 2c below. No significant changes were noted in MDA concentrations in experimental groups.

3. 2. 4. Glutathione peroxidase concentrations in Experimental Groups

The effect of the administration of Viagra and doses of Local Rejuvenator on Glutathione peroxidase (GPx) concentration is presented in Figure 2d below. No significant changes were noted in MDA concentrations in experimental groups.

4. DISCUSSIONS

Local rejuvenator is known to enhance sexual desire and stimulate arousal. Due to its content, this aphrodisiac is believed to stimulate the senses and promote relaxation and arousal (Shin *et al.*, 2010). In this current study, the effects of a locally made rejuvenator on antioxidants and oxidative stress markers were evaluated in male albino Wistar rat models in comparison with Viagra (a standard drug administered for erectile dysfunction).

Superoxide dismutase has proven a useful probe for studying the free radicals in reactions involving oxygen, since it acts as a defense against oxidative tissue damage by dismutation of superoxide radical. In healthy adult's superoxide dismutase values are $149.70 - 207.10$ U/ml. According to the results of this study, the group administered with Viagra showed significantly lower concentrations of SOD as compared to the Control group.

This finding is in line with Afonso *et al.*, (2023). This reveals the negative effects of Viagra on SOD antioxidant enzyme concentration as seen in treated experimental animals. This shows that this drink is able to protect cells from oxidative stress associated with many locally prepared concoctions.

Catalase catalyzes the breakdown of hydrogen peroxide into water and oxygen. This enzyme is of great importance as it protects the cell from oxidative damage caused by reactive oxygen species. The normal value of catalase is $(107.7 \pm 14.4 \text{ MU/l}) - (117.9 \pm 16.8 \text{ MU/l})$. The results from this study showed the lowered concentration of catalase in the Viagra group as compared to the control. This agrees with Roopha & Padmalatha, (2012). This states the toxic effect of drugs such as Viagra and its potential to cause antioxidant imbalance.

Malondialdehyde levels in different biological systems can be used as an important indicator for lipid peroxidation both within and outside of cells for various disorders. Normal malondialdehyde levels range from 89 to 195 nM.

The findings from this study indicate no significant changes (positive or negative) in malondialdehyde concentrations and are in contrast with Nguyen *et al.*, (2021).

This suggests that Viagra and locally made rejuvenator may possess little or no capacity to cause oxidative stress due to its inability to increase malondialdehyde concentrations.

Glutathione peroxidase is a cytosolic enzyme that catalyzes the reduction of hydrogen peroxide to water and oxygen as well as catalyzing the reduction of peroxide radicals to alcohols and oxygen. The findings from the study indicate no significant difference between the control group and experimental groups.

The observed improvement in superoxide dismutase and catalase activities in rejuvenator treated rats suggests that the drink may modulate redox homeostasis by reducing the generation of reactive oxygen species (ROS).

This aligns with previous reports that dietary antioxidants contribute to enhanced sperm quality and reduced lipid peroxidation in reproductive tissues (Houda et al., 2021). The absence of significant changes in MDA levels indicates that lipid peroxidation was well controlled, further supporting the antioxidant capacity of Rejuvenator.

Overall, these results suggest that Rejuvenator may exert protective physiological effects through its antioxidant potential, which could contribute to improved reproductive performance and systemic health. However, comprehensive mechanistic studies are needed to confirm the exact pathways involved.

Limitations

This study was limited by its relatively short duration and small sample size, which may not fully represent long-term or chronic effects of Rejuvenator administration. Further studies involving hormonal assays, histopathological evaluation, and prolonged exposure are recommended to validate these findings and provide deeper mechanistic insights.

5. CONCLUSION

The Local libido and fertility enhancer was successfully tested on the rats and the effects it had on on LD50, Body weight changes, antioxidants and oxidative stress parameters was determined. It does not possess the tendency to increase free radical activity in the system. However, there is tendency of weight gain from its consumption.

The results of this study revealed the anti-oxidant potential of rejuvenator, a sexual enhancer. This shows its protective potentials against free radicals. The use of locally made rejuvenator can be more effective and have less toxic effects compared to phosphodiesterase type 5 (PDE5) inhibitors such as Viagra.

List of Abbreviation

LD50 – Lethal Dose 50

SEM - Scanning emission microscopy

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